

The Impact of Quality Service and Price for the Satisfaction Customer on APRIL.COM Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

The problem in this research is the lack of quality of customer satisfaction. This research aims to determine the increase in customer satisfaction results by implementing service quality and price. This type of research is quantitative research carried out at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar. The research subjects are incoming customers. Totaling 60 people. Data collection techniques in research are interviews, observation, documentation studies, and questionnaires to see customer satisfaction during the business process. Data analysis techniques are carried out in several stages, namely data quality testing, classical assumption testing, and hypothesis testing. Based on the coefficient of determination (R^2), the adjusted R square value (is 0.590), which means that the influence of the independent variable (X) on variable Y is 59%. This can indicate that the variables Service quality (X1) and price (X2) explain the influence on the variable customer satisfaction customers at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar is 59% while the remaining 41% is the influence of other independent variables that were not examined in this research. These factors include the location of APRIL.COM which is quite far from the campus area and main roads. Which will affect customers who come because there is competition within the same store and distance. It can be concluded that implementing service quality and price can increase customer satisfaction at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar in the coming year

INTRODUCTION

1. Setting Behind

The increasing development of technology and information and communication systems creates more openness to tough competition, so that every company will work hard in its efforts to satisfy customers so that the company gets loyal customers. This is more because customers are increasingly intelligent, price conscious and demanding. , customers can access a lot of information and also a lot of other product information that customers can access, making customers even more spoiled for product choices via the internet.

Quality as interpreted by ISO 9001 is a combination of traits and characteristics that determine the extent to which output can meet customer requirements. It is the customer who determines and assesses to what extent the traits and characteristics meet his needs. This definition of quality shows that quality is closely related to achieving the expected standards.

Apart from service quality, another factor that is no less important in determining satisfaction is customer value. Consumer satisfaction will be realized if the perception of the value obtained is more than the sacrifice made. Referring to the results of research examining the relationship between customer value, satisfaction and loyalty, it shows that customer value has a significant effect on consumer satisfaction, and consumer satisfaction has a significant effect on consumer loyalty. The dimensions of service quality, customer value and satisfaction show the results that service quality and customer value significantly and positively influence consumer satisfaction.

The definition of price is stated as the relative value of a product or service and is not a definite indicator to show the amount of resources needed to produce a product or service. There are several indicators that characterize prices, namely as follows: 1. Affordable prices for goods, 2. Price matches with quality, 3. Price competition, 4. Prices match benefits, 5. Price perceptions can influence consumers in making decisions.

Consumer/customer satisfaction is influenced by three main variables, namely Conformity to expectations, Interest in visiting again, Willingness to recommend, then consumers get satisfaction, ultimately creating consumer loyalty.

2. Research Objectives

In accordance with the problem formulation above, the objectives of this research are:

1. To determine the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction.
2. To determine the effect of price on customer satisfaction.
3. To determine the effect of service quality and price on customer satisfaction

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Definition Quality Service

According to Tjiptono in Meithiana Indrasari (2019:61), service quality is a dynamic condition that is closely related to products, services, human resources, as well as processes and the environment that can at least meet or even exceed the expected service quality.

According to Tjiptono, the definition of service quality is an effort to fulfill needs accompanied by consumer desires and the accuracy of the delivery method in order to meet customer expectations and satisfaction. It is said that *service quality* or service quality is the fulfillment of customer needs and desires and the accuracy of delivery to match expectations customer.

According to Kotler and Armstrong in Meithiana Indrasari (2019:61) service quality is the totality of the features and characteristics of a product or service that supports its ability to satisfy needs directly or indirectly. Quality service products have an important role in shaping customer satisfaction. The higher the quality of the products and services provided, the higher the satisfaction felt by customers. If customer satisfaction is higher, it can generate profits for the business entity. One of the main ways to maintain a service company is to consistently provide services with a higher quality of service than competitors and meet customer expectations.

Indicators Quality Service

According to Lupiyoadi and Hamdani in Meithiana Indrasari (2019:63) there are several dimensions or attributes that need to be considered in service quality, namely:

1. *Tangibles*

Tangibles are the ability of a company to demonstrate its existence to external parties. The appearance and capability of the company's physical facilities and infrastructure that can be relied upon by the condition of the surrounding environment is concrete evidence of the services provided by the service provider.

2. *Reliability*

Reliability is the company's ability to provide services as promised accurately and *reliably*. Performance must be in accordance with customer expectations, which means punctuality, the same service to all customers without errors, a sympathetic attitude, and high accuracy.

3. Responsiveness (*Responsiveness*)

Responsiveness (*Responsiveness*) namely a policy to help and provide fast (*responsive*) service and appropriately to customers, by conveying clear information.

4. Guarantees and Certainty (*Assurance*)

Guarantee and Certainty (*Assurance*), namely the knowledge, politeness, guidance and ability of company employees to grow customers' trust in the company. This includes several components, including communication, credibility, security, competence and *courtesy*.

5. Empathy (*Empathy*)

Empathy is providing sincere and individual or personal attention given to customers by trying to understand consumer *desires*. Where a company is expected to have understanding and knowledge about customers.

Definition Price

According to Samsul Ramli in Methiana Indasari (2019:51), the definition of price is stated as the relative value of a product or service and is not a definite indicator to show the amount of resources needed to produce a product or service. according to Swastha in Meithiana Indrasari (2019:39) price is the amount of money (plus the product if possible) needed to get a number of combinations of products and services And According to Ginting in Meithiana Indrasari, price is the amount of money that consumers have to pay to get the product.

According to Buchori Alma (2013:269) in Meithiana Indrasari, price is the amount of money paid for services, or the amount of value that consumers exchange in order to get benefits from owning or using goods or services.

Indicators Price

According to Fure (2013:276) indicators used to measure prices include:

1. Affordable product prices
Prices that can be reached by all groups according to the selected target market segment.
2. Price matches the quality
The quality of the product determines the price that will be offered to consumers.
3. Price competition
The price offered is whether it is higher or below average than competitors
4. Prices that match the benefits
Consumers will feel satisfied when they get benefits after consuming what is offered according to the value they spend.
5. Price perceptions can influence consumers in purchasing decision.
When the price does not match the quality and consumers do not get benefits after consuming it, consumers will tend to hesitate in making the decision not to make a purchase. Conversely, if the price is appropriate, consumers will make a decision to buy.

Satisfaction Customer

Satisfying consumer needs is the desire of every company. Apart from being an important factor for a company's survival, satisfying consumer needs can increase excellence in competition.

Consumers who are satisfied with products and services tend to repurchase the product and reuse the service when the same need arises again in the future. This means that satisfaction is a key factor for consumers in making repeat purchases, which is the largest portion of the company's sales volume.

Consumer satisfaction is the level of consumer feelings after comparing what he received and his expectations (Umar in Meithiana Indrasari, 2019: 82). A customer, if he is satisfied with the value provided by a product or service, is very likely to remain a customer for a long time.

According to Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller, quoted from the book *Marketing Management* in Meithiana Indrasari, Consumer Satisfaction is a person's feeling of joy or disappointment that arises after comparing the performance (results) of the product in mind against the expected performance (2019:82).

Indicators Satisfaction Customer

Tjiptono in Meithiana Indrasari, (2019:92) Because there are so many customers who use the product and each customer uses it differently, has a different attitude, and speaks differently. In general, satisfaction programs have several indicators, namely:

1. Matching expectations
It is the conformity of the expected performance of a product with what customers perceive, including promotion, price and quality of the product provided.
2. Interest in visiting again
Willingness of customers who are willing to return to visit the company or business.
3. Willingness to recommend
Customers who are willing to recommend the company/business to friends, relatives or relatives.

The framework for thinking in research is as follows:
Kualitas pelayanan X_1

(Sumber : Penulis (2023))

Keterangan :

- Secara Simultan
- - - - - Secara Parsial

Figure 2. 1 Framework Conceptual

METHODS

Types Study

The type of research used in this research is quantitative research . Based on the research objective, namely to measure how much influence service quality and price have on customer satisfaction at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar, this type of research uses quantitative methods. Quantitative methods can be interpreted as research methods that are based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research populations or certain samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative statistical data analysis with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses.

3.2 Research instrument And Technique data collection

Research instrument

Sugiyono's research instrument (2017: 102) is a data collection tool used to measure observed natural and social phenomena. The research instrument used in this research is in the form of a questionnaire or questionnaire which contains questions related to the research variables .

Table 3. 1

Research Instrument Grid

No	Variable	Indicator	Statement number	Number of questions
Service quality (X₁)				
1	Tangible	Complete facilities	1	3
		Adequate building	2,3	
2	Reliability	Ability	4	3
		The product is good	5,6	
3	Responsiveness	Good and precise service	7,8	3
		Readiness	9	
4	Guarantee and Certainty	Security	10	3
		Extensive knowledge	11,12	
5	Empathy	Understand customer needs	13,14	3
		Correct service time	15	
Price (X₂)				
6	Affordable item prices	Provide affordable prices	16,17,18	3
7	Price match with quality.	Providing quality according to price	19,20,21	3
8	Price competition	Able to understand price competitiveness	22,23,24	3
9	Prices that match the benefits	Price benefits	25,26,27	3
10	Price perceptions can influence consumers in	Determination Decision making	28,29,30	3

	making decisions			
Customer Satisfaction (Y)				
1	Matching expectations	Results received	31.32	2
2	Interested in visiting again	Friendly and Trust	33,34	2
3	Willingness to recommend	Offering Process	35.36	2
Amount				36

Furthermore, the instrument will be measured using a Likert scale to produce accurate data. Sugiyono (2017:93) suggests that the "Likert Scale" is used to measure the attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. The answer to each instrument item using a Liket scale has a gradient from strongly agree to strongly disagree, which can be in the form of words including:

Table 3. 2
 Score Alternative Answer

Information	Score
SS = Strongly Agree	5
S = Agree	4
KS = Disagree	3
TS = Disagree	2
STS = Strongly Disagree	1

((Source: Sugiyono, (2019:93))

Scores on the Likert scale are used for questions or questions that have a positive value. The score weight will have the opposite value, if the question or statement is negative.

Technique Data collection

The strategies used to obtain the required data are known as data collection techniques. The following data collection techniques were used in this research:

Interview (interview)

This data collection technique is based on self-reports or self-reports, or at least on personal knowledge and/or beliefs. Sutrisno Hadi in Sugiyono (2017) stated that the assumptions that researchers need to hold in using the method interviews and questionnaires are as follows:

1. That the subject (Respondent) is the person who knows best about himself
2. That what the subject states to the researcher is true and can be trusted.
3. That the subject's calm understanding of the questions the researcher asks him is the same as what the researcher intended.

Sugiyono (2017:138) states that interviews can be conducted in a structured or unstructured manner and can be done face to face or using the telephone. Structured interviews are used as a data collection technique, if the researcher or data collector knows for sure about the information that will be obtained. Unstructured or open interviews are used in preliminary research or even for more in-depth research about

respondents. This research conducted structured interviews by asking the same questions to APRIL.COM Pematang Siantar customers

Observation

Sutrisno Hadi in Sugiyono (2017) suggests that observation is a complex process . an organized process from various biological processes And psychological . two among the most important are observation processes And memory .

Technique data collection with observation used if if , research regarding with behavior human, process work , symptoms natural And when observed respondentsno _ too big. Appropriate method This researcher do observation in a way direct about behavior And transaction on APRIL.COM Pematang Siantar .

Study Documentation

According to Arikunto Suharsimi (2014:201), Documentation originate from the word document , which It means goods written.study documentation this is gaining And learn data from Journal Book as well as ter internet sites hook with supporter APRIL.COM Pematang document Siantar .

Questionnaire

According to Sugiyono (2019:199) , Questionnaire is technique collector and data carried out with method give set question or question written to respondents to answer . questionnaire is Wrong One explanation from every the variables that exist within study it 's starting from variable X (Quality Service And Price) and variable Y (Satisfaction Customer).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Data Analysis Techniques

Test Data Quality

Test validity

Suharsimi Arikunto (2014:211) Validity is a measure that shows the levels of validity or authenticity of an instrument. A valid or valid instrument has high validity. On the other hand, an instrument that is less valid means it has low validity.

The correlation formula that can be used is the one proposed by Pearson, known as the product moment correlation formula, which is calculated using SPSS 2022.0 for Windows software.

Test Reliability

Suharsimi Arikunto (2014:221) Reliability refers to the understanding that an instrument can be trusted enough to be used as a data collection tool because the instrument is good. A good instrument will not be tendentious in directing respondents to choose certain answers. can be trusted, which is reliable will produce data that can be trusted too. A reliable measuring instrument is a measuring instrument that has a high level of reliability and can be trusted. Reliability refers to the level of reliability of something. Reliable means, trustworthy, so it can be relied on. In this research, to measure reliability using the Cronbach's Alpha formula (Suharsimi Arikunto 2014:221) with the help of SPSS 22.0 for Windows software.

According to Wiratna Sujerweni (2014), a questionnaire is said to be reliable if the Cronbach alpha value is > 0.60 .

Test Hypothesis

Multiple Linear Analysis

Multiple regression analysis, namely the analytical technique used to determine that there is a functional relationship between a number of variables X and one variable Y. The form of the multiple regression analysis equation is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \epsilon$$

Information :

Y	= Customer Satisfaction
a	= Constant
X ₁	= Service Quality
X ₂	= Price
b ₁ , b ₂	= Regression Coefficient
ε	= Residual Error

Test Partial (t test)

According to Ghozali (2013), the t test is used to test the hypothesis partially to show the influence of each independent variable individually on the dependent variable. The t test is an individual significance test. This test shows how far the independent variable is partially from the dependent variable. The form of the test is as follows:

1. Ho: b₁ = 0, meaning independence has no effect on service quality. Ha: b₁ ≠ 0 means independence has an effect on customer satisfaction.
2. Ho: b₂ = 0, meaning that competence has no effect on customer satisfaction. Ha: b₂ ≠ 0, meaning that competition has an effect on customer satisfaction. Data processing will be carried out using SPSS software so that the resulting data is more accurate.

Test Stimulant " (F test)

According to Ghozali (2016), the F test aims to find out whether the independent variables together have an effect on the dependent variable. The F Test (Simultaneous Test) is to see whether the independent variables together have a significant influence on the dependent variable. Hypothesis testing uses the F Test or what is usually called Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). ANOVA testing or F test can be done in two ways, namely by looking at the significant level or by comparing with F_{hitung} tests F_{tabel} with a significant level in the anova table $\alpha = 0.05$ then Ho is rejected (influenced), conversely if the significant level in anova >math>\alpha = 0.05</math> , then Ho is accepted (has no effect).

Test Coefficient Determination (R²)

Once the coefficient is known and to see how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable, the coefficient of determination (Kd) is used with the following formula:

$$Kd = r^2 \times 100 \%$$

Information :

Kd = Coefficient of determination

r = correlation coefficient.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Analysis Descriptive

In this study, the instrument used in the list of statements has a service quality variable (X1) consisting of 3 statements for tangible indicators, 3 statements for reliability indicators, 3 statement items for the responsiveness indicator, 3 statement items for the guarantee and certainty indicator, 3 statement items for the empathy indicator. For the price variable, 3 statement items for the price indicator (X2) of affordable goods, 3 statement items for the price conformity indicator with benefits, 3 statement items for the price competition indicator, 3 statement items for the price indicator according to benefits, 3 statement items for the price perception indicator which can influence consumers in making decisions. and for the customer satisfaction variable (Y) consisting of 2 statement items for the conformity to expectations indicator, 2 statement items for indicators of interest in revisiting, and 2 statement items for indicators of willingness to recommend. This research questionnaire was distributed to 50 customers on APRIL.COM Pematang Siantar.

To find out the general situation, the following is a description of respondents on APRIL.COM Pematang Siantar:

1. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender

Table 4. 1

Characteristics Respondent Based on Type Sex

Gender	Number of people)	Percentage (%)
Man	18	30 %
Woman	42	70 %
Amount	60	100%

Source: Results of Statistical Data Processing (2023)

Based on table 4.27 above, it shows that the majority of respondents were women, namely 32 respondents or 64%, while The remaining 18 male respondents or 36%.

This shows that female customers prefer trust, comfort and affordability when using APRIL.COM Pematang Siantar services.

1) Characteristics of Respondents Based on Occupation

Table 4. 2

Characteristics Respondent Based on Work

Type of work	Number of people)	Percentage (%)
Student/Students	40	67%
civil servants	8	16%
Private Employee	5	10%
Self-employed	4	8%
Other	3	6%

Total	60	100%
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Source: Results of Statistical Data Processing (2023)

Based on table 4.28 above, it can be seen that of the 50 respondents who have carried out transactions on APRIL.COM Pematang Siantar, consisting of 30 people or 60% of respondents are students, 8 people or 16% of respondents are civil servants, 5 people or 10% of respondents are private employees, 4 people or 8% of respondents are self-employed and 3 people or 6% of respondents are respondents who do not have various/appropriate types of work. It is known that the majority of customers consist of students due to time constraints, location and price adequate.

2) Characteristics of Respondents Based on Intensity of Using Services

Table 4. 3

Characteristics Respondent Based on Intensity Use service

Frequency(/Year)	Number of people)	Percentage %
1-5 times	3	5%
6-10 times	7	12%
11-15 times	10	33%
>16 times	30	50%
Total	60	100%

Source: Results of Statistical Data Processing (2023)

Based on table 4.29 above, it is known that of the 50 respondents who were sampled, 25 people (50%) of respondents have become APRIL.COM Pematang Siantar customers who come > 16 times/year, 11-15 times/year the respondents are 15 people (30 %) respondents. This shows that customer loyalty to continue making transactions and using APRIL.COM Pematang Siantar services is still quite high.

Hypothesis Test Results

Test Multiple Linear Regression

The multiple linear regression test carried out in this study aims to find out that the variables Service Quality (X1) Tangible (*Tangibels*), Reliability (*Reliability*), Responsiveness (*Responsives*), Guarantee and Certainty (*Assurance*), Empathy (*Emphaty*), and the variable Price (X2) (affordable price of goods, suitability of price to quality, price competition, price in accordance with benefits, price perception can influence consumers in making decisions) influence Customer Satisfaction (Y).

The following is the calculated t value obtained for partial hypothesis testing using the help of SPSS 21 software.

Table 4. 4

Results Test Coefficient Regression Multiple

Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-1,359	3,087		-.440	,662
1 Service quality	.153	.033	,405	4,673	,000
Price	,266	.031	,738	8,521	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

(Source: SPSS 21 data processing results)

Based on the table data above, the multiple regression equation obtained in this research is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 \cdot X_1 + b_2 \cdot X_2 + \epsilon$$

$$Y = -1.359 + 0.153 X_1 + 0.266 X_2 + 164.449$$

In the equation above, it can be seen that the interpretation is that the value of -1,359 is a constant or condition when the Customer Satisfaction variable is before it is influenced by other variables, namely the Service Quality variable (X1) and the Price variable (X2). If the independent variable does not exist then the Customer Satisfaction variable will not experience change.

b_1 (The regression coefficient value

b_2 (regression coefficient value

t test

The following is the calculated t value obtained for partial hypothesis testing using the SPSS 21 software program.

Table 4. 5

Results T Test (Partial)

Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1,359	3,087		-.440	,662
	Service quality	.153	.033	,405	4,673	,000
	Price	,266	.031	,738	8,521	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

(Source: SPSS 21 data processing results)

1. First hypothesis testing (H1)
It is known that the sig value for the influence of
2. Second Hypothesis Testing (X2)
It is known that the sig value for the influence of

Test f

The results of joint hypothesis testing between variable X1 and variable X2 against Y can be seen in table 4.34 below with the help of the SPSS 21 program:

Table 4. 6 Results F Test (Simultaneous)

ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	236,284	2	118.142	40,950	,000 ^b
	Residual	164,449	57	2,885		
	Total	400,733	59			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

b. Predpictors: (Constant), Price, Service Quality

Based on the output table in table 4.34 above, the significance value obtained for the influence of Service Quality (X1) and Price (X2) simultaneously on Y is $0.000 < 0.05$ and the calculated F value is $40,950 > F$ table 3.156, so it can be concluded that H3 is accepted, which means that there is a simultaneous influence of X1 and X2 on variable Y.

Test Coefficient determination

The value of the coefficient of determination (R²) is used to measure the magnitude of the influence of the independent variables which consist of Tangible , Reliability , Responsiveness , Assurance , Empathy , affordable price of goods, suitability of price to quality, price competition, prices are in accordance with benefits, price perceptions can influence consumers in making decisions regarding Customer Satisfaction at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar.

Table 4. 7
 Results Coefficient Determination (R²)

Model Summary^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,768 ^a	,590	,575	1,699

a. Predictors: (Constant), Price, Service Quality

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

(Source: SPSS 21 data processing results)

Based on table 4.35 above, the Adjusted R Square value (coefficient of determination) is 0.590, which means the influence of the independent variable (X) on variable Y is 59%. This shows that the variables Service Quality (X1) and Price (X2) explain The influence on the Customer Satisfaction variable of Customers at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar is 59% while the remaining 41% is the influence of other independent variables which were not examined in this research. These factors include the location of APRIL.COM which is quite far from the campus area and where the highway will affect customers who come because there is competition within the same shop and the distance.

CONCLUSION AND RECCOMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion described in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

1. There is a partially significant influence between service quality variables consisting of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, guarantee & certainty and empathy on customer satisfaction in using the services provided by APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar. This shows that customer satisfaction at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar can be influenced by tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance & certainty and empathy.
2. There is a partially significant influence between price variables consisting of affordable goods prices, suitability of prices to quality, price competition, prices in accordance with benefits, price perceptions can influence consumers in making

decisions regarding customer satisfaction in using the prices provided by APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar. This shows that customer satisfaction at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar can be influenced by affordable prices of goods, suitability of prices to quality, price competition, prices in accordance with benefits, price perceptions can influence consumers in making decisions.

3. There is a significant simultaneous influence between service quality variables consisting of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, guarantee & certainty and empathy, price variables consisting of affordable goods prices, suitability of prices to quality, price competition, prices in accordance with benefits, price perceptions can influencing consumers in making decisions regarding customer satisfaction in using the services and prices provided by APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar. This shows that customer satisfaction at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar can be influenced by tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, guarantee & certainty and empathy, affordable price of goods, suitability of price to quality, price competition, price in accordance with benefits, price perception can influence consumers in taking decision.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the conclusions above, it is recommended as follows:

1. Service quality which consists of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, guarantee & certainty and empathy is an important part that influences customer satisfaction at APRIL.COM Pematangsiantar. This can be done by increasing the ability of employees to carry out the promised services accurately and reliably. according to what the customer wants.
2. Prices consist of affordable prices for goods, suitability of prices to quality, price competition, prices in accordance with benefits, price perceptions can influence consumers in making decisions. This can be done by increasing the ability of price promotions to carry out promised service prices accurately and reliably according to what customers want.
3. It is recommended that future researchers find other variables that support the higher value of service quality and price, so that apart from increasing the knowledge that researchers gain, companies can also consider continuing to improve services through other supporting variables, such as price factors and so on.
4. For HKBP Nommensen PEMATANGSIANTAR University, this research can be used as reference material or knowledge study for future researchers and as a guide for additional knowledge, especially in entrepreneurship courses at the FKIP faculty and advanced entrepreneurship for economic education.

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